

Antecedents and Consequences in Job Insecurity on Employee: A Narrative Systematic Review

¹Bella Christianty
Master of Psychology
Gunadarma University
Jakarta, Indonesia

²Era Ayu Amelia
Master of Psychology
Gunadarma University
Jakarta, Indonesia

³Siti Qori Almira
Master of Psychology
Gunadarma University
Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- Increased global competition due to continuous change results in an era of progress, especially in the economic sphere. The uncertain economic situation poses a threat to employee job security. Of course, at this time employees feel their jobs are at stake. Job insecurity is defined as a mismatch between what individuals want and what individuals get. This study was conducted to further discuss what are the antecedents and consequences of job insecurity in employees. This study uses a systematic review method with narrative techniques. A total of 27 selected journals were used for review. From the analysis of this journal, the antecedents of job insecurity are grouped into two, those from the organization and the environment, as well as those from individuals. Similarly, the consequences of job insecurity are grouped into two, those to the organization and the individual. Thus, this study suggests organizations pay attention to the tendency of job insecurity in employees and handle it with open communication, employee involvement, and job resources. Meanwhile, employees need awareness to increase personal resources.

Keywords:- Job Insecurity; Employee; Antecedents; Consequences.

I. INTRODUCTION

Change and renewal are constantly carried out by humans to create an increasingly advanced era. The progress of this era, of course, has an impact on human life, including the economic sphere, both positively and negatively. Unlimited space and time is a positive impact of the times, so it makes all individuals or companies the right to compete freely in the international market. Where this indicates that there is increasing global competition (Bohle, Chambel, Medina, & Cunha, 2018). Various unexpected economic situations, such as the implementation of mergers, downsizing, outsourcing, acquisitions, the use of robots, automation and artificial intelligence in certain jobs, and other types of structural changes can threaten employee job security

and create uncertain working conditions (Karatepe, Rezapouraghdam, & Hassannia, 2020).

Of course, at this time employees feel their jobs are at stake (Richter & Näswall, 2018). In Indonesia, the loss of jobs such as toll booth guards, since the mandatory payment with electronic money has made employees lose their jobs (Badan Pengatur Jalan Tol, 2017). In addition, some jobs are even predicted to disappear, as explained by the Minister of State-Owned Enterprises (Badan Usaha Milik Negara/BUMN), Erick Thohir, that jobs such as food preparation service personnel, office administration personnel, transportation service personnel, non-auto manufacturing production personnel, construction and extraction, traditional farming, fishing, and forestry, sales and related fields, social media managers, and security service personnel are expected to disappear by 2030, resulting in the need for competency development of workers (CNBC Indonesia, 2022).

Thus, this shows that many things need to be considered in supporting success in competition amid advancing times. Based on research conducted by Price Waterhouse Coopers (2022), human resources are at the first level which is a threatening risk to company growth so human resources are an important means for company growth. The importance of human resources for company growth certainly makes companies strive to have employees who have abilities that are relevant to what is needed in company growth. Human resources are not only the responsibility of a company but also the responsibility of the employees themselves. Given, the competition that is becoming increasingly severe as a result of the times, requires employees to continue to improve their quality to be able to survive in the work competition. Competition to maintain and develop careers among employees is part of job insecurity. Job insecurity is a feeling of employee helplessness in maintaining the desired continuity in a threatening work situation (Greenhalgh & Rosenblatt, 1984).

Job insecurity also according to Greenhalgh and Rosenblatt (2010) influences dysfunctional work attitudes, such as decreased effort, turnover intention, and resistance to change. Shoss (2017) also revealed that job insecurity is not just worried about losing a job, but job insecurity is perceptual, future oriented and uncertain, referring to the opportunity to lose the job as a whole, deterioration in working conditions, and loss of anticipated opportunities. Of course, this will later affect organizational effectiveness, such as low productivity, high employee turnover, and low adaptability (Greenhalgh & Rosenblatt, 2010). In addition, job insecurity does not only cause adverse influences related to attitudes in work settings but more than that. Job insecurity can reduce psychological well being, as well as increase psychosomatic tendencies and physical strain (De Witte, 1999). This is in line with what De Witte, Elst, and De Cuyper (2015) revealed that uncertainty about one's job is an experience that tends to last a long time, and is harmful to health and well being in the short and long term. The continuous experience of uncertainty has a cumulative impact.

Therefore, this study was conducted to systematically analyze the antecedents and consequences of job insecurity in employees. In this study, it is hoped that both companies and employees can find out what can be the antecedents and consequences of job insecurity. Thus, companies can produce human resources that will support the growth of the company, and employees can improve their quality to be able to compete in their work healthily.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to De Witte, Elst, and De Cuyper (2015), job insecurity is a mismatch between what an individual wants (certainty about the future of the individual's current job) and what the individual gets (perception of threats to the current job). Job insecurity is multidimensional, as explained by Hellgren, Sverke, and Isaksson (1999) that job insecurity consists of quantitative job insecurity and qualitative job insecurity. Quantitative job insecurity is explained as employees' worries about their current job in the future, while qualitative job insecurity is related to feelings of threat due to deterioration in work relationships such as worsening working conditions, reduced career opportunities, and decreased salary development.

In addition, Greenhalgh and Rosenblatt (2010) also gave their opinion regarding the dimensions of job insecurity, which are desired continuity, threat, job features, and powerlessness. Desired continuity, is employees do not always want a permanent position, sometimes employees are happy to quit, especially if there is an attractive severance package. Employees also sometimes want to quit if they don't like the work situation or want a more interesting job. Threat is the employee's perception that there will be a possibility of a situation that violates expectations of continuity. That is, this threat is subjective, although it may or may not happen, and this creates job insecurity. Job features at risk, where employees worry about changes that could lead to job loss. Powerlessness is when employees perceive that their jobs are

at risk and employees are unable or unwilling to fight back, so making employees vulnerable to threatening situations.

Job insecurity itself is influenced by several factors, where according to De Witte, Elst, and Cuyper (2015), three things can reduce job insecurity, which are communication, participation, and employability. Ashford, Lee, and Bobko (1989) also gave their opinion regarding the factors of job insecurity, which are perceived lack of predictability and control, organizational changes, role ambiguity, and external locus of control. Kinnunen (2014) added several things that become individual factors in experiencing job insecurity related to the personal background; how the individual's position in the job, usually related to the position identified by the length of work and work contracts concerning working hours; besides that the status in the family is also a factor, where the head of the family who has a higher role in being responsible for supporting the family if they lose their job it can be a big threat so that they are more vulnerable to experiencing job insecurity; as well as attitudes and personality.

Job insecurity itself has a negative impact on employees' physical health, mental health, and psychological well being, such as increased stress, burnout, job exhaustion, and mental distress. In addition, job insecurity also has an impact on employee work attitudes, such as decreased job satisfaction, increased turnover intention, decreased trust in the organization, and decreased commitment to the organization (De Witte, Elst, & Cuyper, 2015; Kinnunen, 2014; and Ashford, Lee, & Bobko, 1989).

III. METHOD

A. Procedures

Study to find antecedents and consequences of job insecurity in employees was conducted by reviewing literature collected from various sources, including Google Scholar, Emerald, Elsevier, Routledge: Taylor and Francis Groups, Wiley Online Library, MDPI, Sciendo, SAGE Publication, Academia, Springer, JSTOR, Medical Care, Peuradeun Scientific Journal, Widya Cipta, and Atlantis Press. This study uses a systematic review method with narrative techniques in the data processing process. Narrative review is used to identify a topic by summarizing, selecting, and focusing on the literature as evidence related to the topic of interest (Koszyána, Csizmadia, & Katona, 2021).

B. Analyzed Data Criteria

From these sources, several journals that are suitable for the proposed study topic were collected, which are 27 journals with publication years 2013-2021. The keywords used during the literature search are job insecurity in the workplace of employees, the impact of job insecurity in the workplace, job insecurity factors, job insecurity antecedents, job insecurity consequences, and job insecurity antecedents and consequences.

The journals found included the Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management, Ethical Theory and Moral Practice, Advances in Developing Human, Article

Sustainability, Contemporary Educational Psychology, Studies in Business and Economics, Journal of Business Research, The International Journal of Social Sciences, Journal of Workplace Behavioral Health, Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Management, Economics, and Business, Global Journal of Enterprise Information System, European Journal of Management and Business Economics, Marketing Intelligence & Planning, South African Journal of Business Management, Problemy Zarządzania - Management Issues, International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences, Journal of Informetrics, Journal of Secretarial and Management, Economic and Industrial Democracy, Business Ethics Quarterly, International Journal of Hospitality Management, International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, Journal of Business Management, Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance, Journal of Occupational Health Psychology, Human

Resources Management Journal, and European Journal of Business and Management.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After collecting data and reviewing, it was found that job insecurity is not just a worry felt by employees for fear of losing their jobs (Shoss, 2017), but job insecurity also involves satisfying the fundamental needs of employees (De Witte, Elst, & De Cuyper, 2015). Where according to Maslow (1943), humans have five basic needs, which are physiological needs, security needs, love needs, self esteem needs, and self actualization needs. This shows that job insecurity has several consequences on individuals, not only as employees but also as humans themselves. Job insecurity can occur due to several antecedents. Antecedents and consequences found in several studies related to job insecurity will be described in detail in Table 1.

TABLE I. SELECTED FINDINGS FROM RELATED LITERATURE

Authors (Year)	Significant Findings
Abolade (2018) pp. 14-15	The research found a negative relationship between job insecurity and organizational performance which in this case explained that the higher the job insecurity, the lower the overall organizational performance, further calculations found that job insecurity had an influence of 40,33% on organizational performance. The study also found that there is a very strong positive relationship between job insecurity and employee turnover.
Asfaw and Chang (2019) pp. 102 and 104	Job insecurity decreases engagement by 37%. Further calculations show that supervisor support can help reduce the negative consequences of job insecurity on engagement.
Aybas, Elmas, and Dündar (2015) pp. 199	Job insecurity has a positive relationship with burnout. Job insecurity felt by employees will increase burnout. Employees who are still working after going through redundancy, downsizing, and privatization programs, tend to experience "survivor syndrome", but employees also anticipate losing their jobs. This leads to burnout.
Bloom, Richter, Hallsten, Svedberg (2015) pp. 54-57	There is a positive relationship between job insecurity and burnout. In addition, job insecurity is also positively correlated with depressive symptoms. Employees who experience job insecurity tend to report more complaints about symptoms of poor mental health, such as burnout and depressive symptoms.
Bohle, Chambel, Medina, and Cunha (2018) pp. 399 and 401	Significantly, job insecurity is a negative predictor of employee performance, where research results show that there is a negative relationship between job insecurity and job performance. To minimize the negative influences of job insecurity, it is necessary to develop good communication with employees in expressing their expectations of the organization.
Bouzari and Karatape (2018) pp. 9-10	Job resources have a negative correlation with job insecurity. Employees who feel job resources (such as selective staffing, continuous training in development, and career opportunities) will tend to have low job insecurity. This means that these programs will motivate employees to learn and improve skills and behavior, as well as opportunities for career advancement in the organization, so this will reduce the job insecurity felt by employees.
Chalim (2018) pp. 209	Job insecurity significantly negatively influences job satisfaction, meaning that job satisfaction will increase if job insecurity decreases. In addition, job insecurity significantly negatively influence organizational commitment, meaning that organizational commitment will decrease if job insecurity increases.
Cheung, Wu, and Chi (2018) pp. 9	Job insecurity is positively related to anxiety and negatively related to job satisfaction. It was also found that psychological capital and perceived employability as personal resources were negatively correlated with job insecurity.
Chirumbolo, Callea, and Urbini (2020) pp. 244	Job insecurity, especially in the quantitative aspect of employees (related to worry about threats and fear of losing their jobs), as well as its qualitative aspect (in the form of perceptions of the potential loss of something important in their work) provides a negative relationship with task performance. While job insecurity with counterproductive work behaviors has a positive relationship that can be seen from the contradictory or deviant behavior of employees in the workplace.
Darvishmotevali and Ali	The direct relationship that can be seen between job insecurity and job performance leads

Authors (Year)	Significant Findings
(2020) pp. 6	to a negative relationship. Where this indicates that if employees have high job insecurity, it results in low job performance. Vice versa, if employee job insecurity is low, there is a high increase in job performance.
Etehad and Karatepe (2018) pp. 13-14	Job insecurity is negatively related to self efficacy where insecurity means employees feel limited control and a feeling of helplessness against threats can hinder employee growth and learning which has a negative influence on self efficacy, besides that job insecurity has a positive influence on absenteeism or employee absence at work.
Glambek, Matthesen, Hetland, and Etnarsen (2014) pp. 261-262	Workplace bullying is said to be one of the causes or antecedent factors of increased employee job insecurity. Both variables have a negative relationship, where exposure to workplace bullying ultimately makes employees feel afraid, uncomfortable when working, and the loss of valuable aspects at work so that employees have thoughts of escape and cause the intention to leave work within six months.
Ismail (2015) pp. 269-272	There is a positive influence between job insecurity on intention to quit. This shows that high job insecurity in employees will tend to have a high intention to quit as well. Job insecurity contributes 52,6% to intention to quit. In addition, job insecurity also has a positive influence on burnout, with a contribution of 15,9%. Managers must convey a clear message that the organization feels responsible and values employees.
Karatepe, Rezapouraghdam, and Hassannia (2020) pp. 8-9	Job insecurity directly has a strong negative influence on employee work engagement. While for cases that occur in employees with the intention of not attending work (absenteeism) and not having non-green behaviors in the scope of work, together is the result of the positive influence of job insecurity. In addition, job insecurity also illustrates a positive relationship between intention to be late for work and intention to leave work early. Based on the threat rigidity thesis, transactional theory of stress, social exchange theory, COR theory, and reformulation of attitude theory, it is said that the responses displayed by employees under uncertainty arising from the threat of job insecurity as a stressor and limited job resources (training, supervisors, support) certainly trigger employees' concerns about their security at work. From the things that have been mentioned, finally, employees tend to respond poorly to their work, such as a decrease in work engagement, high levels of unfriendly behavior, and an increase in absenteeism, which in turn also results in nonattendance intentions in the form of intention to be late for work and intention to leave work early.
Lawrence and Kacmar (2016) pp. 69	Job insecurity has a significant and positive relationship with emotional exhaustion. High levels of employee emotional exhaustion will reduce available resources and in turn, result in a lack of ethical decision making. Of course, this will lead employees to engage in unethical behavior. However, unethical behavior can be avoided or minimized by increasing adaptability and embeddedness in the organization.
Lin, Chen, Ashford, Lee, and Qian (2018) pp. 173-174	Job insecurity is negatively related to Organization Based Self Esteem (OBSE). The negative relationship between job insecurity and OBSE will also be stronger for employees with more proactive personalities than less proactive employees. It also found that OBSE was positively related to job performance and affective commitment.
Pienaar and De Witte (2016) pp. 40	Sense of coherence and work locus of control, have a role in predicting job insecurity. Sense of coherence is stronger in causing job insecurity than work locus of control. It may be due to the greater stability of sense of coherence in the personality construct. Sense of coherence and work internal locus of control are negatively correlated with job insecurity. That is, when someone has a high sense of coherence and work internal locus of control, job insecurity in employees will be low, and vice versa.
Rafiq and Chin (2019) pp. 6-9	Job insecurity has a negative relationship with life satisfaction of employees. It means that the higher the job insecurity, the lower the life satisfaction of employees. Job insecurity not only causes stress from work but damages overall well being in various cultures and industry settings.
Rajput and Talan (2017) pp. 7-8	By 29,3%, role ambiguity and perceived organizational change together can potentially cause job insecurity. Perceived organizational change is higher than role ambiguity in causing the impact of job insecurity. In the end, job insecurity has an adverse impact on physical health by 11,4%, this is because employees live in constant fear which causes lethargy and less time for exercise, so which later causes diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, and so on. Meanwhile, job insecurity adversely affects mental health by 15,3%. Role ambiguity tends to make employees feel a lack of control over work, thus making employees experience job insecurity.

Authors (Year)	Significant Findings
Richter and Näswall (2018) pp.99-10	Job insecurity has a direct effect on decreasing employee trust, job satisfaction, and mental health with lower values. This means that employees have anxiety related to the future of their work which has a negative influence on employees.
Saeed, Hassan, Dastgeer, and Iqbal (2021) pp. 12-16	There is a negative relationship between perceived job insecurity and work related well being. Effective organizational communication and employee involvement (such as involvement in decision-making and compensation rewards) can reduce perceived job insecurity in employees. Perceived employability as personal resources (such as skills and expertise) can also prevent perceived job insecurity in employees. Then, job insecurity ultimately has a positive relationship with emotional exhaustion.
Selenko, Makikangas, Mauno, and Kinnunen (2013) pp. 536	Overall, the relationship between job insecurity and job performance is described as having a negative relationship. It has been explained that at lower and moderate levels of intensity, job insecurity is negatively related to job performance. While at high levels, the effect is less negative. This is also due to the influence of decreasing or increasing enthusiasm for doing work, including a sense of optimism and supervision.
Shin, Hur, Moon, and Lee (2019) pp. 3 and 7-9	Job insecurity has a negative relationship with intrinsic motivation, in turn, job insecurity will also be able to influence employee performance and behavioral outcomes (organizational citizenship behavior, and change-oriented organizational citizenship behavior). Intrinsic motivation is very important in generating work efforts because employees will consider the motivation to work that arises due to interest and enjoyment at work, regardless of the rewards that will be obtained later. If employees have high job insecurity, then employee perceptions are directed towards feelings of not having meaning at work and control over their work, so employees consider their efforts at work to be meaningless. This certainly causes harm to the development of intrinsic employee motivation which is considered very important in the development, encouragement, and desire to achieve good results at work.
Soelton, Amaelia, and Prasetyo (2019) pp. 172-173	Job insecurity significantly has a positive influence on burnout. It means that if employees feel high job insecurity in their jobs, it will increase burnout in employees.
Soomro, Kundi, and Kamran (2019) pp. 82-85	Job insecurity has a positive correlation with work stress in employees. In addition, job insecurity is also positively correlated with deviant behavior (interpersonal deviance and organizational deviance). In this study, it was found that employees who experience work stress due to job insecurity are under threat of losing resources. Employees engage in deviant behavior to recover from adverse effects or gain additional resources.
Stankevičiute, Staniškiene, and Ramanauskaite (2021) pp. 11-12	Job insecurity is negatively related to job satisfaction where high job insecurity will cause a decrease in job satisfaction, affective organizational commitment, and work engagement. Then based on this, job insecurity is negatively related to happiness at work, meaning that it interferes with employee happiness at work.
Vujičić, Jovičić, Lalić, Gagić, and Cvejanov (2015) pp. 44	There is a negative relationship between job insecurity with job satisfaction and organizational commitment. It means that the higher the job insecurity owned by employees, the lower the job satisfaction and organizational commitment owned by employees.

Based on the literature review conducted, it provides information related to several antecedents that lead to job insecurity, and then consequences as a result of job insecurity in employees. From the results found, researchers further grouped the antecedents of job insecurity into two, which are those from the organization and environment, as well as those from individuals. Just like the antecedents, the consequences of job insecurity are grouped into two, which are those for the organization and the individual.

A. Antecedents of Job Insecurity

➤ Organization and Environment

The causes of job insecurity in employees can come not only internally, such as individual personalities, but also externally, such as the environment and the organization where employees work. Hartley (1999) emphasized that job insecurity arises due to individual interpretation and

evaluation of the external environment. After reviewing journals, it was found that job insecurity antecedents from the organization and environment include organizational communication, job resources, role ambiguity, organizational change, employee involvement, and workplace bullying.

Communication in the organization aims to pass information from the organization to all employees so that employees get relevant, important, and timely information related to work, as well as the conditions and situations of the workplace (Jiang & Probst, 2014). Communication in an organization that is timely and open, will tend to increase the predictive and control ability of employees regarding what will happen in the future, as well as provide experiences to employees related to feelings of being valued and respected by the organization (De Witte, Elst, & Cuyper, 2015). Employees who tend to feel they have information related to their working conditions will help create a sense of security

(Huang, Niu, Lee, & Ashford, 2012). This is supported by research conducted by Saeed, Hassan, Dastgeer, and Iqbal (2021), which shows that effective communication in the organization will reduce job insecurity felt by employees.

Job resources are various aspects of work that employees can use in achieving work goals; overcoming work demands and the impacts; and support employee growth, learning, and development (Wilkinson, 2022). Hobfoll (2001) stated that if employees face stressors that become obstacles at work, then to deal with these stressors they can utilize job resources. The application of job resources at the workplace can be in the form of implementing training and development programs, providing support from superiors and coworkers, selective staffing, and career opportunities (Bouzari & Karatepe, 2018; Karatepe, Rezapouraghdam, & Hassannia, 2020). Based on Bouzari & Karatepes (2018) research, added that providing adequate job resources for employees can reduce job insecurity and encourage employee job expectations. Where these expectations include personal resources that allow employees to be motivated to learn and improve skills and behavior, to create opportunities for career advancement in the organization. With low job insecurity, employees will feel more satisfied at work which in turn employees can find various ways to realize expectations and achieve target goals.

Role ambiguity refers to a lack of certainty, clarity, and predictability regarding work (McCormack & Cotter, 2013). According to research by Rajput and Talan (2017), role ambiguity has the potential to cause job insecurity, because role ambiguity tends to make employees feel a lack of control over work, thus making employees feel insecure about their jobs.

Organizational change refers to the process of change in an organization or system that has been damaged to a more improved state (Rajput & Talan, 2017). However, according to research also conducted by Rajput and Talan (2017), organizational change has the potential to cause job insecurity in employees. It is because organizational change is often perceived as a threat to employees (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), especially at the beginning of organizational change (Schumacher, Schreurs, Van Emmerik, & De Witte, 2015). At the beginning of the change, employees do not have enough time and resources related to change information, so they tend to assess organizational change as unfair (Rajput & Talan, 2017).

Employee involvement is the involvement of individuals in the overall organization and their work. Also defined as a measure of a person's performance that influences personal satisfaction (Wicaksono, 2007). Saeed (2021) based on the results of research conducted, revealed that employee involvement is negatively correlated with job insecurity. It is explained that the average employee who is involved in a job reflects insecurity about the job. So that to feel safe at work, employees are obliged to follow the applicable work procedures and this is what makes them more involved. Employees tend to be involved in arrangements related to decision making, information dissemination, and case solving.

Workplace bullying refers to the phenomenon that occurs to employees when targeted in negative actions by coworkers or superiors where there is a formal or informal power imbalance that causes helplessness for various defenses and resistance because it is hindered by the recognition of the power. Workplace bullying can occur both in the short and long term, at least during the span of one time a week or for example for six months (Glambek, Matthesen, Hetland, & Etnarsen, 2014). Bullying that occurs in the workplace is divided into two: (a) work related bullying which concerns the process of working, such as the loss of employee delegation, an unfair attitude of superiors by deliberately not giving promotions, manipulation of employee performance evaluations, giving excessive workloads, sabotaging certain jobs and so on; (b) personal bullying concerns personal employees who are intimidated through various treatments and words from coworkers or superiors, such as isolation, discrimination/exclusion, neglect, gossip, physical violence, personal jokes, and so on (Bartlett & Bartlett, 2011). Workplace bullying can be a factor that causes employee job insecurity if the bullying treatment from coworkers is based on a certain threat related to job continuity that makes employees unable to move or just fight back. Helplessness and threats that may endanger employees over time can increase job insecurity, so causing fear and worry at work (Glambek, Matthesen, Hetland, & Etnarsen, 2014).

➤ *Individual*

After reviewing the selected journals, it was found that job insecurity antecedents can come from employees themselves. The antecedents of job insecurity that come from individuals are related to psychological capital, perceived employability, work internal locus of control, and sense of coherence.

Psychological capital is a state related to the development of positive psychology in individuals characterized by (a) efficacy to support success in challenging tasks; (b) optimism about current and future success; (c) hope, which directs to always be on the road to goals in achieving success; and (d) resilience, which is to survive and rise when faced with difficulties to achieve success (Luthans, Morgan, & Avolio, 2015). Meanwhile, **perceived employability** is related to individual perceptions regarding the possibility of getting and keeping a job (Vanhercke, De Cuyper, & Peeters, 2014). Guilbert, Bernaud, Gouvernet, and Rossier (2016) revealed that employability will facilitate individual career outcomes, both current and long term.

Employees who have personal resources in jobs will tend to be less likely to lose their jobs, so this will reduce job insecurity in employees (Saeed, Hassan, Dastgeer, & Iqbal, 2021). It is proven through research conducted by Cheng, Wu, and Chi (2018) that psychological capital and perceived employability which are personal resources have a negative correlation with job insecurity. It shows that the higher the psychological capital owned by employees, the lower the job insecurity owned by employees. Likewise with perceived employability.

Sense of coherence, which is a global orientation that shows the extent to which individuals have a sense of self confidence that tends to be dynamic and enduringly where (a) stimuli from the external internal environment in the course of an individual's life are structured, predictable, and explainable; (b) individuals have the resources to meet the demands arising from these stimuli; and (c) these demands are a challenge that is considered worthy of individual investment and involvement (Antonovsky, 1987). Sense of coherence is a personal resource that supports individuals to face challenges and stressors in the work environment (Pearlin & Schooler, 1978). Whereas according to Saeed, Hassan, Dastgeer, and Iqbal (2021), personal resources in the work environment will tend to make employees less vulnerable to job loss. Thus, in research conducted by Pienaar and De Witte (2016), sense of coherence is negatively correlated with job insecurity, which means that the higher the sense of coherence, the lower the perceived job insecurity.

Work internal locus of control. According to Spector and O'Connell (1994), locus of control is a personality variable related to general individual expectations regarding whether individuals can control reinforcement in their lives or not. Individuals who have an internal locus of control are individuals who have expectations that they can control reinforcement, while individuals who have an external locus of control are individuals who have expectations that force or luck from outside is controlling the reinforcement. Thus, it is concluded that work internal locus of control is employees who have the expectation that they can control reinforcement at their work. Work internal locus of control has a negative correlation with job insecurity, meaning that the higher the work internal locus of control, the lower the job insecurity, and vice versa (Pienaar & De Witte, 2016). It may be because one of the dimensions of job insecurity is powerlessness, as a form of inability or unwillingness of employees to provide resistance (Greenhalgh & Rosenblatt, 2010) so that when employees feel that can control work, job insecurity felt by employees decreases. As stated by Greenhalgh & Rosenblatt (1984), that powerlessness tends to be disturbing for employees who have internal locus of control.

B. Consequences of Job Insecurity

➤ Organization

Job insecurity felt by employees can have an impact on the organization in various aspects. Based on a review of the literature, it was found that the consequences of job insecurity on organizations are that it influences organization performance, organizational commitment, turnover intention, organization based self esteem, job performance, task performance, work related well being, happiness at work, work stress, burnout, organizational citizenship behavior, job satisfaction, work engagement, and counterproductive work behaviors.

Organization performance relates to the extent to which the performance of the organization moves to achieve its goals. Organizational performance is the cumulative result of the overall performance of its employees, where employee performance can be affected if employees feel job insecurity.

Research conducted by Abolade (2018) explains how job insecurity influences organizational performance by 40.33% so higher job insecurity leads to lower overall organizational performance. So, high job insecurity among employees will certainly hamper the organization's efforts to achieve its goals.

Organizational commitment is defined as the level at which employees identify with the organization and all its goals and the desire to remain as part of the organization (Robbins & Judge, 2018). In line with this, Jex (2002) explains that organizational commitment is related to the extent of employee dedication and willingness to work for the organization. The research found that organizational commitment will be low with high job insecurity (Chalim, 2018; Vujičić, Jovičić, Lalić, Gagić, & Cvejanov, 2015) so this explains how job insecurity influences organizational commitment. Furthermore, Robbins and Judge (2018) explain how important commitment is to employees, where if employees currently feel unhappy with the jobs, committed employees are likely to be willing to continue working for the organization.

Turnover intention is an individual's desire to leave the current job consciously deliberately to find better job opportunities in other companies (Tedja & Sijabat, 2021). Turnover intention is divided into three cognitive categories. First, thoughts of leaving refer to the employee's consideration of leaving work. Second, search intention refers to the employee's decision to look for work outside the organization. Third, employees have decided to leave the organization someday. There are several reasons employees choose to change jobs, including salary oriented job satisfaction factors, reasons for self development, lack of comfort at work (job insecurity) and the environment, lack of facilities provided, and related job autonomy (Priherdityo, 2016; Clercq, Azeem, Haq, & Bouckenooghe, 2020). In connection with these reasons, based on the results of the study also found that there is a very strong positive relationship between job insecurity and employee turnover (Abolade, 2018).

Organization based self esteem (OBSE) was defined by Pierce, Gardner, Cummings, and Dunham (1989) as an employee's belief to fulfill needs by participating in the organization, where employees see themselves as important and can be useful as members of the organization. The research found that OBSE will be high if employee job insecurity is low (Lin, Chen, Ashford, Lee, & Qian, 2018). OBSE is a belief that employees have in their role in the organization which will further lead to the performance produced during work. Research conducted by Lin, Chen, Ashford, Lee, and Qian (2018) also found that OBSE is positively related to job performance, where increasing OBSE will also increase job performance.

Job performance is a set of activities and processes carried out by employees in their work to achieve certain goals. The research found that job performance will increase if job insecurity in employees is low (Bohle, Chambel, Medina, & Cunha, 2018; Darvishmotevalia & Ali, 2020; Selenko, Makikangas, Mauno, & Kinnunen, 2013). Job performance is the overall value of the work done by

employees during a certain time where the results will help the organization achieve its goals (Motowidlo, Borman, & Schmit, 1997). Job performance consists of three dimensions, job dedication, interpersonal facilitation, and task performance. Where job insecurity affects one of the dimensions of job performance, which is task performance of employees (Wyland, Lester, Mone, & Winkel, 2013). **Task performance** is a combination of employee effectiveness and efficiency in performing core job tasks (Robbins & Judge, 2018). Motowidlo, Borman, and Schmit (1997) explain that task performance has two types, where the first is related to the activity of converting raw materials into goods or services as a result, and the second is related to the activities of serving, maintaining, and distributing products, or preparing planning, coordination, supervision to run effectively and efficiently. Research by Chirumbolo, Callea, & Urbini (2020) found that high job insecurity will be associated with low task performance. So job insecurity will certainly harm the organization in achieving goals due to the poor performance produced by employees on core work and as a whole.

Work related well being can be basically understood by looking at the meaning of the word well being itself. In the APA Dictionary of Psychology (2022) well being is explained as happiness and satisfaction in individuals, with low stress levels, and having good physical, mental, or quality of life health. Scott-Jackson and Mayo (2018) explain that work related well being emerges as a form of concern for employee health both physical and mental and sees it from the perspective of individual well being, where performance or business results are not too concerned. Research finds work related well being will increase with low perceived job insecurity (Saeed, Hassan, Dastgeer, & Iqbal, 2021). Rothmann and Cooper (2008) assert that one of the contributing factors to low well being in employees is the absence of job security such as job security in the near future and being able to remain at the same level of work. The effect of poor well being will affect the work performance of employees when it has crossed the tolerable threshold so it will further affect the organization as a whole (Rothmann & Cooper, 2008).

Happiness at work is identified by Jones (2010) as a mindset that allows individuals to maximize performance and potential at work, by paying attention to how when working alone or in groups. Fisher (2010) states that one of the factors that cause employees to feel insecure at work is the lack of happiness at work. As the saying goes that happy employees are productive employees, it turns out to be true. Happiness at work includes feelings of pleasure related to how the job is, what the characteristics of the job are, to the overall organizational context (Fisher, 2010; Stankevičiute, Staniškiene, & Ramanauskaite, 2021). In line with this statement, based on research conducted by Stankevičiute, Staniškiene, & Ramanauskaite (2021), the results found that job insecurity is negatively related to happiness at work. Job insecurity is considered one of the stressors that interfere with and reduce employee happiness at work.

Work stress is explained by the World Health Organization (2020) as an individual response when faced with job demands and pressures that do not match the employee's knowledge and ability to cope. In this case WHO explains that one of the things that can lead to stress is work context such as job status, where it relates to job insecurity. Research by Soomro, Kundi, and Kamran (2019) also confirms that increasing job insecurity in employees will also increase the work stress experienced. In addition, job insecurity can also lead to **burnout** which in the APA Dictionary of Psychology (2015) is defined as physical, emotional, or mental fatigue in individuals accompanied by decreased motivation, performance, and the emergence of negative attitudes towards both self and others. Research has found the influence of job insecurity on burnout, in which case high job insecurity leads to high employee burnout (Aybas, Elmas, & Dündar, 2015; Bloom, Richter, Hallsten, & Svedberg, 2015; Ismail, 2015; Soelton, Amaelia, & Prasetyo, 2019). Work stress and burnout are employee conditions that are feared will have an impact on their work activities so that they can harm the organization. Therefore, stress and burnout must be addressed as soon as possible to ensure the long term sustainability of the organization (Kerr, 2022).

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is defined by Robbins and Judge (2018) as voluntary behavior performed by employees that is not part of the employee's formal job requirements, and contributes psychologically and builds the social environment in which he works. OCB is one of many aspects related to employees with organizations where its application will be beneficial to the organization. OCB is a behavior performed that can help the organization become more efficient and effective (Organ, Podsakoff, & MacKenzie, 2006). Confirming this, Gemmiti (2007) explained that OCB is an important aspect for the organization to function optimally which is closely related to the overall productivity of the organization through the behavior of its employees. OCB includes employees who speak positively about their organization, help other employees, and do more than the expectations given for their work (Robbins & Judge, 2018). Based on research, employee OCB can be influenced by job insecurity (Shin, Hur, Moon, & Lee, 2019). Therefore, knowledge and arrangements related to job insecurity are needed so that it does not cause effects that are feared to reduce the value and function of the organization.

Job satisfaction is explained by Tangkilisan (2007) as the level of pleasure felt by employees for their role or work in the organization. Job satisfaction can affect employee behavior which will further affect the function and performance of the organization as a whole (Spector, 2022). Employees who have satisfaction at work also feel positive feelings related to work, while employees who do not feel satisfied will have negative feelings (Robbins & Judge, 2018). Robbins and Judge (2018) continued that job satisfaction can affect job performance and organizational citizenship behavior in employees, whereas job dissatisfaction can lead to counterproductive work behavior such as absenteeism and turnover. Based on this, it is important to pay attention to employee situations that can lead to dissatisfaction, which one

is job insecurity. The research found that low job satisfaction is a consequence of high job insecurity (Chalim, 2018; Cheung, Wu, & Chi, 2018; Richter & Näswall, 2018; Stankevičiute, Staniškiene, & Ramanauskaite, 2021; Vujičić, Jovičić, Lalić, Gagić, & Cvejanov, 2015).

Work engagement is defined as a mind filled with positive feelings, satisfaction with work, characterized by passion and dedication to the job (Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzales-Roma, & Bakker, 2002). Employees who are engaged with the work tend to feel like achieving more challenging goals. It is not uncommon for employees to exert full capacity in solving problems and developing innovative services related to employees personal commitment in order to realize their goals (Bakker & Leiter, 2010). If employees no longer feel fully connected to the job role, there may be a stressor that is hindering employee growth, development, and learning orientation. One such stressor is job insecurity, which can reduce the intensity of engagement of employees when working. Job insecurity is said to have the potential to thwart employee efforts and impede employee progress toward ultimate achievement. Employees will find their jobs no longer challenging. Where this describes the situation when employees no longer feel safe, then employees will not fully work engagement. The reason is that employees certainly feel worried about the results of their work and even experience greater frustration (Karatepe, Rezapouraghdam, & Hassannia, 2020). This statement is proven through research results that high job insecurity will cause decrease in work engagement, where job insecurity directly has a strong negative influence on employee work engagement (Karatepe, Rezapouraghdam, & Hassannia, 2020; Stankevičiute, Staniškiene, & Ramanauskaite, 2021).

Counterproductive work behaviors (CWBs) refer to any employee behavior that is intentionally performed and judged to be contrary to the legitimate interests of an organization. The focus here is more on how the behavior itself, regardless of what the consequences are afterward (Gruys & Sackett, 2003). Chirumbolo, Callea, and Urbini (2020) stated that several studies that discussed the positive relationship between job insecurity and CWB found that employees who often engage in deviant behaviors show a tendency towards insecurity in the workplace. Related job insecurity has been discussed in the research of Karatepe, Rezapouraghdam, and Hassannia (2020), revealed that the response to job insecurity in employees is a sense of worry about employees' security at work which is triggered by uncertainty, and the end it makes employees tend to behave poorly towards their work, such as a decrease in work engagement, high levels of nongreen behavior, and an increase in absenteeism, which in turn also results in nonattendance intentions in the form of intention to be late for work and intention to leave work early.

➤ *Individual*

Based on the review conducted in the selected journals, job insecurity has consequences on the individual itself, which are related to physical and mental health, self efficacy, intrinsic motivation, and trust.

Physical and mental health, the research conducted by Rajput and Talan (2017) shows that job insecurity has a negative impact on physical health and mental health. Physical health deteriorates as a result of job insecurity, because employees live in constant fear, causing lethargy and lack of time for exercise, which will eventually lead to diseases, such as diabetes, hypertension, and so on (Rajput & Talan, 2017). Employees who experience job insecurity report more complaints about symptoms of poor mental health, such as depressive symptoms (Bloom, Richter, Hallsten, & Svedberg, 2015). Research conducted by Cheung, Wu, and Chi (2018) also shows that job insecurity is positively correlated with anxiety. Similarly, research conducted by Lawrence and Kacmar (2016) showed that job insecurity has a significant positive relationship with emotional exhaustion.

Self efficacy refers to an individual's feeling of belief in the ability to carry out and organize what actions are needed to manage situations that have prospects (Bandura, 1997). Self efficacy can be influenced by the emotional arousal of situational circumstances (Bandura, 1976). When situations with more difficult performances with higher feared risks, cause individuals to experience fear and unbearable obstacles, so will not do what is feared (Bandura, 1976). It is also what is said in research conducted by Etehadi and Karatepe (2018) that when employees experience insecurity, that is, with limited control and a feeling of helplessness against threats can hinder employee growth and learning which has a negative impact on self efficacy.

Intrinsic motivation is defined by Ryan and Deci (2000) as a form of encouragement to do an activity based on pleasure and inner satisfaction where the movement is not based on rewards or accompanying pressure from outside. Intrinsic motivation is very important for individuals because it is a self initiative in completing work. In motivated employees, it means that there is energy that is activated to achieve work goals. The opposite is also true in the case of unmotivated employees. Ryan and Deci (2000) continue that one factor that influences intrinsic motivation comes from situational and contextual. Where examples that often occur to employees are related to feelings of insecurity when working. Research conducted by Shin, Hur, Moon, and Lee (2019) stated that employees who have high job insecurity can direct their perceptions and feelings that they do not fully have a bond and meaningfulness in work. Therefore, control over their work decreases so employees consider their efforts at work to be meaningless. From this, it is known that job insecurity has a negative relationship with employee intrinsic motivation, which can hinder attachment, fulfillment of autonomy, and hinder employee efforts in achieving good results when working due to decreased interest and enjoyment at work.

Trust generally refers to a strong belief in the truth, strength, ability, and reliability of an individual or organization, and this belief is a form of readiness to be vulnerable to the behavior of others, meaning that it is detached from its ability to control (Wilkins, 2018). Richter and Näswall (2018) said that the decrease in trust based on previous research has been a consequence of employee

insecurity at work. More specifically, it explains how employees lose trust in an organization. On the other hand, Lahno (2001) considers trust as a rational action and emotional response, and therefore if individuals have put a sense of trust in something, then individuals will be able to bear the risk of trusting decisions in certain ways. In the context of employees who have high trust in the organization, it indicates that employees have an interest and a sense of belonging to the same values. However, research conducted by Richter and Näswall (2018), it was found that employees have job insecurity, which has a direct effect on reducing trust to a low level. The result that often occurs is a poor relationship between superiors and subordinates, in addition, there comes a feeling of disappointment because of the loss of the employee's belief system in organizational integrity (how the organization treats employees fairly regarding the fulfillment of promises of employee rights), and employees feel threatened about the future of their work which makes employees feel insecure about their jobs. Of course, if there is no mutual trust in each other, then all parties can be affected (negative effects on employees and downsizing of the organization).

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Job insecurity threatens employees' future employment and the satisfaction of fundamental needs met by employees. Job insecurity perceived by employees, of course, will ultimately affect the effectiveness and productivity of an organization. In addition, this also indicates that job insecurity not only has an impact on employees and organizations within the scope of work, but job insecurity can also have an impact on other aspects of life as individuals themselves. Thus, this study was conducted to provide an understanding of job insecurity, especially related to the antecedents and consequences of job insecurity in employees.

This study used 27 selected journals based on predetermined criteria in accordance with the research objectives to be reviewed. After reviewing, the antecedents and consequences of job insecurity were grouped into two. Antecedents of job insecurity are grouped into which come from the organization and the environment, as well as those from individuals. In the organization and environment, it consists of communication in the organization, job resources, role ambiguity, organizational change, employee involvement, and workplace bullying. Meanwhile, in individuals, there are psychological capital, perceived employability, sense of coherence, and work internal locus of control. Antecedents that come from individuals show that job insecurity is not only the responsibility of the organization but also the responsibility of the employees themselves. The definition given by De Witte, Elst, and De Cuyper (2015) also reveals the subjective perceptions of the employees themselves, so that one employee may feel insecure about his job, but another employee feels confident enough to maintain his job. So, antecedents that come from individuals also need to be considered.

Similarly, the consequences of job insecurity consist of organizations and individuals. Consequences of job insecurity in the organization include organizational performance, organizational commitment, turnover intention, organization based self esteem, job performance, task performance, work related well being, happiness at work, job stress, burnout, organizational citizenship behavior, job satisfaction, work engagement, and counterproductive work behaviors. Summarized from the results found, job insecurity has an impact on overall organizational performance which can hinder the organization in its efforts to achieve its goals. Meanwhile, the consequences of job insecurity on individuals include physical and mental health, self efficacy, intrinsic motivation, and trust. In this case, job insecurity affects employees' physical and mental health, beliefs, interests, and even the beliefs that employees have as individuals. The consequences of job insecurity that have been described, show that job insecurity is quite important to be considered, where to reduce job insecurity felt by employees, is not only the responsibility of the organization, but also the responsibility of the employees themselves.

Researchers suggest paying attention to the antecedents of job insecurity. The results of this study are expected to be useful, especially for the human resource department and managers to better recognize the indications of employees who experience concerns regarding the future of their work, a questionnaire can be used to measure the level of job insecurity of employees or self reported by employees. In addition, organizations can implement an open communication system, increase engagement, build a supportive work culture, facilitate access to counseling, and provide facilities for employees for learning and development, so that in the end it can support the demands of the tasks that must be performed. Job insecurity, which is characterized by subjective perceptions, makes organizations need to pay attention to job resources and employees pay attention to personal resources as mentioned earlier to be able to make employees feel they have control and the ability to predict the future so that employees tend to feel less job insecurity. One way that employees can support current and future needs is by honing their skills and learning new skills through learning media available offline and online. Future research can use different techniques that are more supportive of widespread data exploration, such as cross sectional approaches, longitudinal data collection, and self reported. In depth analysis can also be conducted to pay attention to differences through demographic data, making the research more meaningful with various supporting literature evidence.

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